

Virtual tourism: A new way of travelling and a new traveller profile

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Abstract

The evolution of technology makes it possible to discover destinations in an immersive way without the need to travel. Through fieldwork based on 415 surveys, this study determines the relationships between the socio-demographic profile, the respondent's self-assessment of the use of technology, video games, virtual reality and the metaverse, with the willingness to carry out different immersive virtual tourism experiences. Using an artificial neural network of the multilayer perceptron type, it was found that youth and prior knowledge of online video games and virtual reality have a decisive influence on the willingness to engage in immersive virtual tourism activities.

Keywords: *virtual tourism, artificial neural network, tourists' profiles*

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1. INTRODUCTION

Technology has made it possible to get to know a remote tourist destination without using a means of transport. Pictorial or photographic representations have traditionally been available resources to get to know a distant place, at least visually. However, virtual reality (VR) has made it possible, not so long ago, to live a much richer and more intense immersive experience. As a result, virtual tourism has revolutionised the industry and the experience linked to certain products (Pedrana, 2014). This type of tourism is based on constructing a visual environment recreated from real landscapes that allow tourists to experience an immersive experience (Bogicevic et al., 2019). In addition, new mixed reality or virtual reality techniques have opened up new possibilities for destination exploration. These techniques make it possible to get to know existing or lost places through digital composition work based on photographs, videos, archival documents, photogrammetry, computer modelling, etc. (Vincent, 2017; Bec et al., 2021). From this material, it is possible to generate VR experiences that include images, movement and sound, but also other mixed experiences that combine real and imagined environments and environments in which the real environment is overlaid in a digital context (Bec et al., 2021). There are, therefore, various levels of immersion in the virtual tourism experience (Beck et al., 2019).

There is a marked and evident difference between face-to-face and virtual tourism. Their comparison must consider how consumption decisions are made, how the experience is evaluated, tourists' behaviour, and their profiles (Zhang et al., 2022). Zhang et al. (2022) have pointed out the need to increase the practical evidence and theoretical framework on virtual tourism to improve knowledge about public sentiment towards this activity. Few studies have studied public sentiment towards virtual tourism (Kim et al., 2020; Lin et al., 2020; Wei et al.,

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